

GUIDANCE ON THE INTERNALISATION OF ESG REQUIREMENTS FOR THE COMBINED EXTRACTION OF HEAT AND MINERALS

Summary:

Every project for the extraction of minerals has to be subject to a PESTEL (political, environmental, societal, technological, economic, legal) analysis to assess its viability. The combined extraction of heat and minerals is no exception.

This document provides Guidance for a self-assessment, focusing in particular on the environmental risks and impacts. The societal, economic and regulatory aspects are covered by other reports produced within the CRM-geothermal project.

To aid the self-assessment this guidance document also contains a comprehensive catalogue of risks that may be relevant for projects of the combined extraction of heat and minerals.

This is document is an extract from CRM-geothermal Deliverable 4.1.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The digital and energy transition in the European Union and worldwide implies an increasing need of raw materials that need to be mined, and provision of Critical Raw Materials (CRM) for the EU is usually linked to import dependency. A potential additional source of CRMs and an alternative to conventional mining could be the exploitation of geothermal reservoirs, as geothermal brines often contain high concentrations of metal ions. The EU-funded 'CRM-geothermal' project aims to open up the potentially huge untapped resource of raw materials from geothermal fluids and provide operators and investors with information needed to assess the viability of the approach of co-extraction heat and minerals from geothermal fluids.

Every project for the extraction of minerals has to be subject to a PESTEL (political, environmental, societal, technological, economic, legal) analysis to assess its viability. The combined extraction of heat and minerals is no exception even though it would not be a classical mining project with respect to the impacts and legacies it may create.

Although it has been shown that any environmental impacts from projects that extract raw materials from geothermal brines will be low, this has to be demonstrated not only to the regulatory authorities, but also to public stakeholders with a view to create trust. A key element of trust-building is a comprehensive assessment of potential risks and impacts together with proposals for their adequate management. In other words, the ESG requirements have to be fully internalised into the project planning process.

In this document, a scheme for the internalisation of ESG requirements is presented, to be implemented through a check-list to accompany the development of combined extraction sites. The check-list takes prospective operators through several steps that help them identify ESG risks along the life-cycle of a facility. The operators are thus enabled to address these potential ESG risks before they become active risks. The report also introduces a reporting standard for sustainability aspects as additional guidance.

The societal and economic aspects feeding into the PESTEL assessment are subject of complementary CRM-geothermal reports, which are informed by the risk assessments laid out in this report.

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1 OBJECTIVES

The EU-funded ‘CRM-geothermal’ project aims to open up a potentially huge untapped resource of critical raw materials (CRM) that can be extracted from geothermal fluids. Combined extraction of heat and minerals maximises returns on investment for geothermal plants, minimises environmental impact and enables domestic supplies of CRM. The objective of the CRM-geothermal project is to provide the necessary information that would help to deploy the combined extraction of heat and minerals as a solution to help Europe fulfil the strategic objectives of the EU Green Deal and the Agenda for Sustainable Development.

Every project for the extraction of minerals has to be subject to a PESTEL (political, environmental, societal, technological, economic, legal) analysis to assess its viability. The **objective of the PESTEL assessments** is to demonstrate that extraction is not only technically feasible (T), but that it is environmentally benign (E), is acceptable to the local communities (S), makes economic sense (E), and can be carried out in line with the applicable legal framework (L). In other words, a project has to meet the respective requirements and is performed under an adequate governance framework.

The **objective of this Guidance** is to provide the tools for demonstrating that projects of combined extraction of heat and minerals fulfil these requirements through a self-assessment. This allows project owners, but also the interested public, if made available, to identify areas of good performance, but conversely also scope for improvement.

This guidance focuses on the environmental aspects, while societal and economic aspects have been covered by complementing reports, namely by Mitchell et al. (2025) on laying out successful stakeholder engagement processes, by Correia et al. (forthcoming) on the economic assessment from an investor and policy-making perspective.

The method of choice for assessing overall environmental impacts are the well-established methods of Life-Cycle Impact Assessments (LCIA). The objective here was also to provide technology and project developers with a tool with which they can select the right methods and optimise them with a view to minimise environmental impacts.

The LCIA then can serve as guidance to prospective operators for further improvement and for selecting the technology with the least embodied energy and carbon footprint. This procedure will ensure that ESG requirements are internalised from the planning stage onwards.

2 WHAT ARE ESG REQUIREMENTS ?

Environmental, Societal and Governance (ESG) requirements are borne out of the need to address issues around risks, impacts, expectations and company behaviour in the context of any extractive operation, including combined extraction. In other words, it revolves around how companies go about addressing environmental and socio-economic risks and how these risks shape the extraction strategy and processes in all relevant dimensions.

In order to define such requirements, it is necessary to define the system boundaries and to specify for what purpose these requirements are formulated. From a project perspective the ESG requirements can be used to assess and mitigate any risks that may adversely affect project implementation. On the other hand, projects may need to be

assessed with respect to their sustainability in a wider sense in order to justify, whether to go ahead with it at all or in the chosen form. Of course, the two aspects are linked and are building on the same set of data and information. A difficulty arises from the fact that 'sustainability' is an only loosely defined concept and may be used and interpreted differently by different stakeholders.

This Guidance aims to give practitioners a tool that can help them in assessing the potential impacts and risks of their projects and thus to identify possible mitigation strategies. This in turn will provide project promoters with arguments in any sustainability or stakeholder acceptance debate that may arise from the project.

Over the past decades a large body of literature on ESG requirements and how to implement them in extraction projects has been accumulated. The importance of ESG aspects for the successful implementation of extraction projects has been acknowledged by including them into the resources and reserves reporting and classification processes for investors). The viability of extraction projects is assessed on the basis of reporting standards, such as CRIRSCO (2024a,b) or UNFC (UNECE, 2019). In the first instance, these describe a mineral occurrence from its geological perspective and the feasibility of extraction and processing from a mining and process engineering perspective with a view to provide investors decision-making information. However, a range of so-called 'modifying factors' are introduced that describe the context of a potential extractive operation, which may help or hinder its implementation.

For the (self-)assessment of operations with respect to their sustainability and with a view to disclose such information in annual reports to the public together with corporate financial and social responsibility reporting (CSR) various standards have been developed, namely those by the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI, <https://www.globalreporting.org>) or the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board, SSAB, <https://sasb.org/>. In 2014, amending earlier Directives, the EU put in place the more comprehensive CSR Directive 2014/95/EU (CEU, 2014b), which applies, however, only to enterprises with more than 500 employees. In 2023 a Regulation was put into place that details the scope of assessments and reporting at a European level for those entities to which Directive 2014/95/EU applies (EC, 2023). A more detailed review of the complex of social responsibility and sustainability reporting initiatives, schemes, and regulations, however, is beyond the scope and purpose of this report. The focus of this report is on the comparison of the potential impacts of combined extraction of heat and metals with that of other extraction methods and not on developing methods of comprehensive sustainability reporting for such undertakings. It is also likely that the respective enterprises will not fall under the Directive 2014/95/EU, which does not preclude them, of course, to voluntarily comply with these requirements.

The **societal dimension** is complex and the reader is referred to Mitchell et al. (2025) and the guidance contained therein for practical advice. It is important not only to enter into a societal dialogue with the local communities, but to also enable these communities to shape it in a way that it serves their needs. This is in fact in line with the MIREU recommendations for obtaining social licensing for operation (SLO) in the mining industry (Tost et al., 2021). The recommendations for internalising societal aspects (Chapter 4) take this into consideration.

In Chapter 3 below the environmental aspects are discussed in more detail. The need for taking ESG aspects into the (economic) equation of extractive operations to avoid risks becoming issues has been nicely summed up by Steele-Schober et al. (2020):

- 1. Not applying the same level of rigour to understanding ESG considerations as we do for other technical disciplines e.g., mine-planning. Because Sustainability is not a clearly delineated discipline, and has an inherently high level of uncertainty – much of which is qualitative, it has not always received the same focus and input as more quantitative disciplines, where we can get a number and know that it's right or wrong to fair, or at least quantifiable, level of certainty.*
- 2. Historically, ESG has been seen as a separate section of a project, aimed at providing some qualitative risk input. The financial impacts of the ESG risks have not always been quantified and the information used to determine appropriate action.*
- 3. Due to a lack of rigour or possible uncertainties, the tendency is to be overly optimistic regarding ESG risk impacts to balance out risk conservatism in other areas, providing a “more spread” picture. Belief in the Board Room and amongst experts from more quantitative disciplines that all ESG risks can be mitigated at the operational phase.*
- 4. ESG issues are often only considered as qualitative risks for too long and therefore projects are unable to mitigate or implement change once these evolve from risks to issues.*
- 5. In many cases, ESG risks become issues that are often project stoppers or significant eroders of value. Earlier and better understanding of the risk case reduces the chances of this occurring, and allows for better up-front decisions to be made.*

3 LIFE-CYCLE RISKS AND IMPACTS - ASSESSMENT AND MITIGATION

3.1 RISK CATEGORIES

The life-cycle risks of extractive operations, including those for the combined extraction of heat and minerals can be grouped into four Focus Areas (FAs):

- FA1 – Exploration
- FA2 – Project development
- FA3.1 – Surface extraction
- FA3.2 – Underground extraction
- FA3.3 – Processing
- FA4 – Closure, remediation and long-term management

Of these, the Focus areas FA1, FA2, and FA3.3 are of particular relevance in the context of combined extraction.

The exploration phase often is also the first moment, when a potential future project comes into contact with the local population. The exploration crew, therefore, needs to be prepared to enter into meaningful interaction with stakeholders in order to prepare the ground for a relationship built on trust (cf. Tost et al., 2021; Mitchell et al., 2025).

A key conceptual approach in all risk assessments is the ‘source – pathway – receptor’ paradigm, or in other words:

What is the cause of the risk? – how can it cause harm? – who or what can be affected?

Risk management can address any of the three elements, but the preference is for treating the source, than if the first is not feasible, the pathway. Removing receptors by, for instance, preventing the access of the public to zones (potentially) at risk should only be the last resort. However, (temporary) receptor removal is a typical risk management method in a technical context by e.g. limiting the amount of time an employee can spend in higher risk parts of a plant, fencing off certain areas, guard rails, etc. The discussions in the following section can all be seen conceptually in this way.

3.2 EXPLORATION

Exploration activities have specific environmental and operational health & safety (OHS) risks associated with them, but at the same time allow to establish the baseline for environmental impact assessments (EIAs) and for planning the future safe operation of combined extraction. Exploration activities may include the following:

- Remote / desktop studies prior to entering the field to undertake Exploration;
- Planning for field operations with minimal impacts and environmental risks in view;
- Mapping and collection of exploration datasets without removing samples for analysis (including geological mapping, geophysical surveys, and any environmental or socio-economic baseline studies that can/should be undertaken at this stage);
- Collection of samples in the field for chemical analysis (including geological, mineralogical, and geochemical sampling);
- Invasive (explosive seismic) or non-invasive (hammer seismic, geoelectric, geomagnetic, geotelluric, etc.) geophysical surveys;
- Exploration drilling and sampling (via a variety of drilling techniques, incl. borehole geophysics);
- Drafting of the mineral and energy resource and reserve disclosure statement (in line with e.g. CRIRSCO or UNFC) with respect to ESG requirements;
- Closure and remediation of the Exploration site(s) if needed.

Perhaps the most invasive operation during exploration is the drilling of boreholes. As boreholes for combined extraction are likely to be very deep, they will pass through various aquifers, which entails the risk of hydraulic short-circuiting and cross-contamination, if not carried out with the necessary care, such as casing. Drilling sites also need to be made safe, so that any spilled drilling fluids, potentially contaminated waters, or drill-chippings can be contained and eventually removed for safe disposal, if needed. The preparation of the drilling-site itself may impact the local flora and fauna and the soil properties. Drilling operations are often noisy and may disturb local fauna as well as people nearby. The construction of access roads and the use of public roads for the transportation of materials and equipment will have further impacts to consider.

Similar considerations apply to seismic reservoir exploration, where also disturbance by blasting or vibro-seismic vehicles may be an issue.

Particular care must be exercised in vulnerable and low-metabolism regions, such as the arctic, alpine, or semi-arid regions, where self-healing of damages to ecosystems will take a very long time.

Exploration will feed into an assessment of resources and reserves compliant with CRIRSCO-aligned standards and/or UNFC. This kind of resource assessment or classification will also consider potential environmental and societal impacts as well as

the governance context of any future exploitation project in form of so-called modifying factors. This means in practice, that the respective potential life-cycle risks for an extractive project should be outlined at this moment.

3.3 PROJECT DEVELOPMENT

While the project development activities *per se* are not likely to entail any environmental or OHS impacts, their outcomes may well do. Planning for the whole life-cycle of the envisaged extractive operation is important in order to reduce its potential impacts in the ESG space. Such planning will encompass in the case of combined extraction of heat and minerals the construction of the various extraction- and injection wells, the siting and construction of the industrial facilities, namely the power-plant and the plant for the extraction of the metal value including storage areas for reactants and products, management facilities for extractive and processing wastes, transport routes for reactants and products, etc.

Lohne et al. (2018) undertook a comprehensive review of life-cycle risk and integrity assessments for high-temperature geothermal wells (see Figure 1 below) and also made suggestions for respective regulations. Of particular relevance during the planning phase is the casing design that intends to prevent short-circuiting between different water-bearing zones. Similarly, well-completion (casing, cementation) according to plan needs to be assured.

Figure 1: Different phases in the life-cycle of a well (Lohne et al., 2018).

Damien et al. (2023) have undertaken a comprehensive review of induced seismicity issues around the Upper Rhine Graben geothermal energy systems and the public and regulatory stance towards them. A seismic monitoring network will need to be set up before the actual drilling and well-enhancing begins. In any case, the development of such systems will be planned and supported by reservoir modelling similar to what is done in the hydrocarbon industry, also looking at the hydrogeochemical aspects.

One aspect during construction that may attract particular attention by the public are measures to increase the permeability, water/heat flows, and reactive surfaces down-hole. Such measures consist of pumping fluids at high pressure into the boreholes with a view to open up fractures and other discontinuities. The fractures etc. are kept open by pumping sand or zirconium spheres into the voids thus created. This technique is/was regularly used by the hydrocarbon industry to increase yield. Public concerns arose due to the use of flow-improving surfactants and the seismic activity caused or triggered. While in combined extraction facilities the use of reactants down-hole is generally not envisaged, there is the risk of seismic events due to the disturbance of the rock-stresses

at depth by the extraction of waters or the ‘fracking’ process. Certain national regulations now forbid ‘fracking’ in the context of hydrocarbon exploitation, but explicitly permit it in the context of using geothermal energy.

The drilling of the various wells will give rise to a small amount of extractive waste, which will need to be managed according to the requirements of the Extractive Waste Directive (CEU, 2006). Any inert components of these wastes probably can be re-used on site for construction purposes. Most other wastes arising from the operation will be typical urban or industrial wastes and have to be managed accordingly.

Project development will include the permitting application procedures, as these will be iterative with more detailed planning. At this moment also the final EIA will be developed together with the mitigation plans for any risks and impacts potentially arising.

OHS risks during plant construction are akin to those of other drilling operations and construction sites and the respective safety at the workplace regulations will apply (namely the Directives 89/391/EEC (CEU, 1989) and 92/91/EEC (CEU, 1992b)).

Interactions with (local) stakeholders will continue from the exploration phase, as stakeholder concerns or preferences may influence the design and mode of operation of the extractive operation.

While combined extraction projects are likely to have a rather long life-time, it is still necessary to make preliminary plans for closure, decommissioning, and long-term management of any extractive waste facilities constructed in particular.

Ideally, the combined extraction plant should also be integrated into the socio-economic fabric of the region.

3.4 EXTRACTIVE OPERATION AND PROCESSING

Unlike for most other extractive operations, the risks and actual impacts from combined extraction operations are expected to be relatively small. Once the plant has been built, there will be little changes to the surface features during the operational phase. All processes take place in closed circuits and inside buildings with virtually no emissions and releases under normal operating conditions. There is no clear distinction between extraction and processing compared to conventional mining, although there may be distinct sections in the plant (cf. Figure 2 below).

The main operating risks would be spills and aqueous releases due to pipe breakages. Safety measures typically encompass the construction of impervious basins around the plants to prevent releases into surface waters or sewers, as well as overflow tanks and similar. Whether the new Industrial Emissions Directive 2024/1785 (CEU 2024) would apply to such installations remains to be seen.

From the OHS perspective, the main operating risks are the accidental exposure to hot and/or acid/caustic fluids, reagent chemicals, and the exposure to steam due to mis-operation or malfunctioning of equipment. Such risks are covered by Directives 89/391/EEC (CEU, 1989) and the subsidiary national workplace regulations. The chemical compounds used in the extraction processes may need to be assessed according to Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006 (CEU, 2006b) for any specific workplace or environmental hazards.

Figure 2: Conceptualisation of a combined extraction system.

It may be debatable, whether the wastes from extracting the metal value from the geothermal fluids are extractive or processing wastes, in other words under which legislation they should fall. Safe management routes will depend on the contents of certain elements or compounds, such as heavy metals, radionuclides, arsenic etc., for which no further use or recycling routes are foreseen. Some of these materials may be used on site for further construction purposes. Compared to other types of extractive operations these quantities will be very small. Organic wastes, such as spent ion exchange resins will need to be managed as industrial waste at licensed disposal or incineration facilities, if they cannot be recycled.

3.5 CLOSURE, DECOMMISSIONING AND AFTER-CARE

Once the combined extraction facility has reached the end of its useful life, e.g. due to temperature draw-down, exhaustion of target minerals, or clogging of the open permeabilities, it will need to be closed in an orderly fashion. This may include a slow re-establishment of the original hydraulic regime, if the combined extraction operation resulted in any such change.

Upon closure, structures above and below ground need to be decommissioned so that they do not constitute any long-term risks and cause in impacts. Once the well-head installations have been removed, the wells need to be capped to prevent foreign items

entering them and causing contamination. Depending on the well design, casings may need to be drawn and certain layers be sealed in order to prevent hydraulic short-circuiting and cross-contamination. Installations and structures above ground will need to be dismantled, if no further use for them is foreseen. Construction materials will be cleaned and decontaminated (if needed), so that they can be re-used or recycled.

Any contamination in the ground from spills etc. will need to be removed and the site remediated, if necessary. Unless there is contamination by heavy metals, hazardous chemicals, or radionuclides, it can be foreseen that most removed materials can be directed to recycling.

Any extractive waste facility constructed during the operation needs to be closed and made long-term stable, if not designed in this way already. Respective guidance can be found in MWEI-BREF (2018).

4 GUIDANCE ON THE INTERNALISATION PROCESS

4.1 OVERVIEW

Based on the work outlined above, a scheme for the internalisation of ESG requirements has been developed, to be implemented through a check-list that accompanies the development of combined extraction sites. The check-list takes prospective operators through several steps to help them identify ESG risks along the life-cycle of a facility. The operators are thus enabled to address these potential ESG risks before they become active risks. The check-list also helps to inform discussions with regulators and other (e.g. civil society) stakeholders.

This check-list consists of two parts, namely on a comprehensive project description that is based on the CRIRSCO reporting template (CRIRSCO, 2024; SAMESG, 2017) and on the extensive risk catalogue in the Appendix. This risk catalogue focuses on the environmental and OHS risks and less on societal or governance issues.

This check-list would be completed first at the project development stage and then updated periodically with the as-built information with a view to check, whether any of the original assumptions has changed.

4.2 COMPREHENSIVE PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The SAMESG (2017) guidance intends to support 'competent persons', i.e. persons with relevant (risk) knowledge, rather than potential (combined extraction) project developers. Thus, the SAMREG guidance is written very much from the investors' perspective and, thus, needed to be reformulated to cover ESG issues from a more general environmental and societal sustainability or strategic impact perspective (Table 1).

Table 1: ESG check-list, adapted from SAMESG (2017).

General
1. Provide a description of organisational structure, systems, policies, procedures and management plans, and governance procedures in place to manage ESG issues.
Key plans, maps and diagrams
1. Provide a map which identifies the locality of sensitive receptors to be included on maps within the project area and at least the zone of influence of the site. All surface water features to be included on maps.
2. Identify and describe the location of any sensitive areas within and around the project area and within the zone of influence of the site.
Legal aspects
1. Outline the applicable ESG legal compliance requirements and any mandatory and/or voluntary standards or guidelines to which the project will (have to) subscribe.
2. Identify the ESG permits, authorisations and licences that will be required. Assess whether there is a reasonable basis to believe that all ESG permits, authorisations and licences can be obtained.
3. In case of an already existing geothermal plant, provide a description of any pending administrative enforcement action such as but not limited to directives or compliance notices instituted against the operation, including a notice received by the operator of an authority's intention to issue a directive or compliance notice, by any authority concerned with the regulation of ESG issues whether or not such pre-compliance notice or compliance notice has been suspended pending corrective action.
4. Provide a description of any known future financial liabilities that arise by virtue of recognised claims, penalties, fines, damages and administrative enforcement action that will become due and payable in future.
Environmental parameters
1. Provide an appropriate analysis of the environmental context within which the project is located (or provide the contents of the mandatory EIA). Give an appropriate analysis of the material aspects and impacts that may need consideration including how existing activities may exacerbate or mitigate existing aspects and impacts.
2. Describe, assess and prioritise the risks associated with any obvious environmental factors that may require modifications to the planned combined extraction project. Focus on issues that are likely to remain significant despite the implementation of proven and economically viable mitigation measures.
External societal and political parameters
1. Provide an appropriate analysis of the external societal and political context within which the project is located.
2. Describe and prioritise current societal and political risks, and potential risks that take into account how activities may exacerbate or mitigate existing risks.
3. Describe any societal and political issues that may have a material effect on the planned project. Include issues that are likely to remain material despite the implementation of proposed mitigation measures.

<p>Internal social parameters</p> <p>1. Describe and assess the risks associated with any obvious internal social factors and/or specific contextual details that could have a material effect on the planned project.</p>
<p>Conformance and compliance audits</p> <p>1. Provide a description of legal compliance audits undertaken, including a summary of material findings and management plans to address these findings.</p> <p>2. Provide a description of ESG management system conformance audits undertaken, including a summary of material findings and management plans to address these findings.</p>
<p>ESG liability</p> <p>1. Describe the closure, societal obligations, rehabilitation plan, activities, remaining liability and compliance costs.</p> <p>2. Provide a description of mechanisms in place to address unplanned closure.</p> <p>3. Describe the bonding obligations in place to ensure that these liabilities can be funded on a qualitative and quantitative basis.</p>
<p>Risk analysis</p> <p>1. Provide a description of the existence of a risk assessment process which has been undertaken to identify material ESG issues. Describe programmes in place to monitor identified material ESG issues.</p> <p>2. Describe how the risk assessment process is integrated with the overall risk management framework.</p>

4.3 RISK CATALOGUES

The potential risks to be considered during an assessment in the Appendix attempt to be fairly comprehensive. This does not mean that all these risks may be relevant for a given combined extraction operation at the same time. The list mainly serves a means to create awareness of potential risks and as a checklist. A considerable number of the risks listed are not specific to extractive operations, but would be associated with the various life-cycle phases of any industrial operation, such as chemical processing plants for instance. Risk arising from well-completion have been added according to Lohne et al. (2018).

The tables of risks in the Appendix are organised by life-cycle phase and environmental compartment or other type of receptor potentially affected. This way of organisation means, that certain types of risks, for instance air emissions, reappear in different categories. It would have been also possible to organise this list by type of risk and then list their possible causes. However, the chosen structure allows to attribute risks more clearly to root-causes in each life-cycle phase for which different control measures might be appropriate. After having gone through the steps, the prospective operator should have a comprehensive overview over the potential ESG issues the operation may face.

4.4 SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING

As noted above, extractive operations are now generally expected to not only provide financial and corporate responsibility reports, but to also report on sustainability aspects. Various reporting standards have been developed over time and the one by the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (<https://sasb.org/>) for ‘Metals & Mining’ is outlined in Table 2 (below) as guidance.

It should be noted that that the SASB standards presented In Table 2 are designed to be applicable world-wide and some elements may not be all relevant in a European context, while for instance OHS-related aspects are covered by the respective directives and regulations of the European Commission, e.g., Directives 89/391/EEC (CEU 1989), 92/91/EEC (CEU 1992b), and 92/104/EEC (CEU 1992a), as well as Regulations (EC) Nos. 1272/2008 (CLP; CEU 2008) and 1907/2006 (REACH; CEU 2006b).

Table 2: Topics covered by the ‘Metals & Mining’ sustainability accounting standard by SASB (<https://sasb.org/standards/download/>).

TOPIC	METRIC	CATEGORY	UNIT
Air Quality	Air emissions of the following pollutants: (1) CO, (2) nOx (excluding N2O), (3) sOx, (4) particulate matter (PM10), (5) mercury (Hg), (6) lead (Pb), and (7) volatile organic compounds (VOCs)	Quantitative	t
Waste & Hazardous Materials Management	Total weight of non-mineral waste generated	Quantitative	t
	Total weight of tailings produced	Quantitative	t
	Total weight of waste rock generated	Quantitative	t
	Total weight of hazardous waste generated	Quantitative	t
	Total weight of hazardous waste recycled	Quantitative	t
	Number of significant incidents associated with hazardous materials and waste management	Quantitative	Number
	Description of waste and hazardous materials management policies and procedures for active and inactive operations	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
Biodiversity Impacts	Description of environmental management policies and practices for active sites	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
	Percentage of mine sites where acid rock drainage is: (1) predicted to occur, (2) actively mitigated, and (3) under treatment or remediation	Quantitative	%
	Percentage of (1) proved and (2) probable reserves in or near sites with protected conservation status or endangered species habitat	Quantitative	%
Security, Human Rights & Rights of Indigenous Peoples	Percentage of (1) proved and (2) probable reserves in or near areas of conflict	Quantitative	%
	Percentage of (1) proved and (2) probable reserves in or near indigenous land	Quantitative	%
	Discussion of engagement processes and due diligence practices with respect to human rights, indigenous rights, and operation in areas of conflict	Discussion and Analysis	n/a

Community Relations	Discussion of process to manage risks and opportunities associated with community rights and interests	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
	(1) Number and (2) duration of non-technical delays	Quantitative	No., Days
Labour Practices	Percentage of active workforce employed covered under collective bargaining agreements	Quantitative	%
	(1) Number and (2) duration of strikes and lockouts	Quantitative	No., Days
Workforce Health & Safety	(1) OHS all-incidence rate, (2) fatality rate, (3) near miss frequency rate (NMFR) and (4) average hours of health, safety, and emergency response training for (a) direct full-time employees and (b) contract employees	Quantitative	Rate
Business Ethics & Transparency	Description of the management system for prevention of corruption and bribery throughout the value chain	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
Tailings Storage Facilities Management	Tailings storage facility inventory table: (1) facility name, (2) location, (3) ownership status, (4) operational status, (5) construction method, (6) maximum permitted storage capacity, (7) current amounts of tailings stored, (8) consequence classification, (9) date of most recent independent technical review, (10) material findings, (11) mitigation measures, (12) site-specific EPRP	Quantitative	Various
	Summary of tailings management systems and governance structure used to monitor and maintain the stability of tailings storage facilities	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
	Approach to development of Emergency Preparedness and Response Plans (EPRPs) for tailings storage facilities	Discussion and Analysis	n/a

4.5 RELATIONSHIP TO ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT (EIA)

The environmental and sustainability aspects will be also informed by the EIA that is certainly required as part of the permitting procedures. These, together with the site-specific risk catalogues will shape the narratives to address any SLO issues as part of addressing the societal and governance aspects. In some jurisdictions environmental and social impact assessments may be collected together in an ESIA. A publicly available comprehensive example for an ESIA for a combined extraction project can be found here: ERM (2024).

The weight to be given to each issue will depend on the outcomes of the stakeholder interaction processes (Mitchell et al. 2025). However, the key messages to stakeholder are likely that the overall environmental impacts and nuisances during the operational phase are likely to be small in comparison to conventional mining operations.

Mousavinezhad et al. (2024) pick up on an aspect that is rarely discussed in the present context, namely the footprint of the operation per tonne of Li produced. The information on land-use varies across the literature. For a typical hard rock plant (such as Greenbushes and Mt. Catlin mines and Tianqi lithium plant in Western Australia), approximately 335 m² per tonne of Li₂CO₃ are used, including open-pit mining areas, tailing dams, and lithium refineries. In brine evaporation pond systems, land is needed

for evaporation ponds, wellfields, processing plants, and disposal areas. Direct land use for a brine evaporation pond resource is estimated to be approximately 3656 m² per tonne of Li₂CO₃ (based on Atacama). Conversely, direct land use in a typical DLE setup is lower, averaging around 16 m² per tonne of Li₂CO₃ for processing plants, and, if the wellfield area is also taken into account, approximately 493 m² per tonne of Li₂CO₃. Additionally, if the source of electricity shifts to solar panels, the land required for solar panel installation must be added to the total land use of Direct Lithium Extraction (DLE).

From an overall sustainability and hence environmental point of view the key message is likely that the CO₂-footprint, the amount of embedded carbon, and the physical footprint (including extractive waste management facilities) will be small in comparison to other extraction techniques.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The Environmental, Societal, and Governance (ESG) assessment starts out from three working hypotheses, namely that

- a) every flux of energy or mass constitutes a potential source of environmental risk,
- b) the combined extraction of heat and metals is likely to have less impacts than conventional metal mining, and
- c) lower mass movements are likely to entail lower societal impacts, both objectively and subjectively.

The key instrument for assessment is a careful stock-tacking of all flows of mass and energy and the associated carbon-footprints. The embodied energy and associated carbon-footprint for ancillary processes and materials, such as reactants or sorption substrates also have to be taken into consideration. Mass-flow diagrams for the extraction processes will have to be developed.

Although it has been shown that any environmental impacts from such projects will be low, this has to be demonstrated not only to the regulatory authorities, but also to public stakeholders with a view to create trust.

A key element of trust-building is a comprehensive assessment of potential risks and impacts together with proposals for their adequate management. In other words, the ESG requirements have to be fully internalised into the project planning process.

In consequence, a scheme for the internalisation of ESG requirements has been developed, to be implemented through a check-list to accompany the development of combined extraction sites. The check-list takes prospective operators through several steps that help them identify ESG risks along the life-cycle of a facility. The operators are thus enabled to address these potential ESG risks before they become active risks.

The check-list helps to inform discussions with regulators and other (e.g. civil society) stakeholders as part of the trust-building processes, eventually leading to a social license to operate (SLO).

This check-list consists of two parts, namely a comprehensive project description that is based on the CRIRSCO reporting template or UNFC classification and on the extensive risk catalogue that is provided in the Annex 2 to this Guidance. This risk catalogue focuses on the environmental and OHS risks and less on societal or governance issues. However, levels of governance in European countries in general are high and give little rise of concern.

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APPENDIX – CATALOGUE OF LIFE-CYCLE RISKS FOR COMBINED EXTRACTION PROJECTS

Exploration		
	Risk category	Impact
Exploration Geologist in the field	Walking on the ground	Disturbance of plant cover and wild-life
	Stream sampling	Turbidity disturbing aquatic life
	Stranger(s) in the area	Inquietude and apprehension among locals
Airborne geophysics	Helicopters and drones	Hovering/low altitude flight disturb wild-life
		Inquietude and apprehension among locals
Ground-based geophysics	Vibroseismic trails	Severe disturbance of plant cover and wild-life due to heavy vehicles
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment
		Disturbance of locals by vibrations
	Explosive seismics	Severe disturbance of plant cover and wild-life due to heavy vehicles and explosions
		Disturbance of locals by vibrations and explosions
		Accidental damage to buildings (windows)
		Contamination from spilled drilling fluids
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment
		Risk from storage and handling of explosives
		Wild fire risk from explosions
	OSH risks from operating heavy machinery	
	Core drilling	Severe disturbance of plant cover and wild-life due to heavy vehicles and explosions
		Disturbance of locals by vibrations and explosions
		Contamination from spilled drilling fluids and chips
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment
		Short-circuiting and cross-contamination between aquifers due to inadequate lining and sealing between aquifers upon completion
		Penetration of surface contamination into unsealed boreholes
	OSH risks from operating heavy machinery	
Transport of equipment and samples	Road vehicles	Road accidents, also involving locals
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment off-road and during maintenance in the field
		Loss of life due to accidents
	Helicopters	Crashes with loss of life
		Environmental contamination due to crashes
		Wild-fires due to crashes
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids when maintained in the field

Planning		
	Risk category	Impact
Strategic planning	Site selection	Location of surface facilities can cause more or less disturbances to the natural environment or human settlements
		Habitat fragmentation by surface installations and extractive waste management facilities
		Cumulative impacts from several mining and other industrial facilities

Construction of wells and surface facilities		
	Risk category	Impact
Site preparation	Removal of vegetation cover	OSH risks associated with vegetation clearance
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids from logging and brush cutting equipment
		Disruption and displacement of wild-life
		Accidental killing of wild-life
		Noise disturbance of locals
	Operation of earth-moving plant	Disturbance of plant cover and wild-life
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids from plant
		OSH of equipment operators
		OSH of on-site staff
		Increased surface erosion and stream turbidity
		Dust generation and off-site dispersal
		Accidents due to operator error
	Off-site transport	Road accidents involving lorries
		Accidents during transport of heavy plant
		Lost loads
	Buildings construction	OSH of crane operation
		OSH of scaffolding work
		OSH of stationary equipment (circular saws, mixers, rammers, ...)
		Dropping hazards (tools and materials form overhead)
Dust and fibres from building materials (on-site and off-site)		
Well preparation	Drilling	Noise and vibration
		Dust generation
		Spilling of drilling fluids
		OSH of drilling equipment operation
	Well completion	Casing failure (rupture, bulging, tearing, deformation, etc.)
		Grouting/cementing failure
	Water	Contamination of water-bearing strata
		Draw-down of groundwater levels
		Cross-contamination of aquifers
	Gas	Radon-release from open boreholes
		Release of noxious or toxic gases from fluids

Plant operation		
	Risk category	Impact
Geothermal plant operation	Operation	Contamination from spilled drilling fluids and chips
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment
		Short-circuiting and cross-contamination between aquifers
		Penetration of surface contamination into unsealed boreholes
		OSH risks from plant operations
		Failure of pressurised vessels and hot pipes
		Accidental spills of reactants or pregnant solutions
		Chemical spills during reactant preparation
	Geological	Seismicity due to re-equilibration of stresses
		Subsidence due to water extraction
	Water	Contaminated effluents
		Failure of hydraulic protection wells
		Failure of decant water treatment systems
	Electrical	Shock due to damaged electrical installations
Natural	Flooding of extraction site	

Extraction and Processing		
	Risk category	Impact
Extraction	Operation	Accidental spills of processing fluids in plant
		Chemical spills during processing fluid preparation
		OSH of plant operation
		Kinetic energy including dropped objects and falls from height
		Failure of pressurised vessels and hot piping
	Water	Accidental discharges of contaminated fluids
		Failure of pipes and tanks
		Failure of decant water treatment systems
		Regional water stress due to extraction of process water
	Air	Olfactory nuisances off-site
Biological	Biohazards e.g. from bacteria used in advanced processing techniques	
Radiation	Naturally occurring radioactive minerals (NORM)	
Electrical	Shock due to damaged electrical installations	
Products	Chemical	Hazardous impurities Hazardous processing agent residues
	Radiation	NORM in products
By-products	Chemical	Hazardous impurities Hazardous processing agent residues
	Radiation	NORM in by-products
Wastes	Chemical	Hazardous components Hazardous processing agent residues
	Radiation	NORM in wastes

Closure and Decommissioning		
	Risk category	Impact
Site abandonment	Operational	Collapse of built structures due to lack of maintenance
	Water	Cross-contamination of aquifers due to improperly lined boreholes
	Radiation	Radon release due to unsealed boreholes
	Electrical	Shock due to damaged electrical installations
	Public safety	Failure of access prevention (collapse of fences) Uncontrolled access to hazardous substances (reagents) remaining on site
Decommissioning	Operational	OSH of dismantling and demolition activities
		OSH of plant and machinery operation
		OSH of site staff
		Exposure to hazardous substances in buildings
		Noise and vibration from demolition activities
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids to the environment
		Loss of hazardous materials from structures being dismantled
		Kinetic energy including dropped objects and falls from height
	Accidents during on-site transport of materials	
	Water	Short-circuiting between aquifers due to changing hydraulic regime
		Leaching of alien substances during hydraulic re-equilibration
		Release of hazardous substances during demolition and dismantling
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids to groundwaters
	Air	Off-site dust from demolition activities
		Release of hazardous minerals (asbestos, silica, NORM,...)
		Dust generation from e.g. crushing of concrete
	Noise	Off-site noise and vibration due to demolition and dismantling activities
	Electrical	Shock due to damaged electrical installations
	Transport	Accidents during off-site removal of materials for recycling or re-use
		Release of hazardous substances during transport to off-site disposal
Societal	Nuisance of demolition activities	

Remediation		
	Risk category	Impact
Wells	Water	Residual lixiviants that cannot be removed by pump-and-treat
		Short-circuiting between aquifers
	Failure of well-casings	
Air	Radon leakage into buildings on site or into the surrounding environment	
External risks	Natural hazards	Damages due to earthquakes
		Changing climatic boundary conditions (e.g. amount and intensity of precipitation)